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Design and analysis of a spoiler for the Audi A4 B8 Avant

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INFO

Technical note

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Abstract

In my publication, I will examine an aftermarket spoiler for an Audi A4 B8 Avant, and I will also present its 3D printing process. The role of the spoiler is to improve the vehicle's aerodynamics, thereby reducing fuel consumption.

For station wagons and hatchbacks, the airflow travels along the roof and then separates from the surface at the rear. In this region, a low-pressure zone is formed, which creates a turbulent vortex. As aerodynamic drag increases, fuel consumption also rises. The purpose of my spoiler is to add an extra lip to the vehicle, directing the airflow further back so that it separates later from the surface. As a result, turbulence and the formed vortex are reduced, leading to lower fuel consumption.

Firstly, I will introduce the necessary concepts (aerodynamics, drag, 3D printing, materials, FEA). Secondly, I will present its function in more detail. Thirdly, I will describe the CAD model and how it was designed. Fourthly, I will analyze how well it withstands the forces acting on it. Fifthly, I will demonstrate the steps and settings of the 3D printing process. Finally, I will summarize the obtained results.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aerodynamics

Aerodynamics is the science that deals with the interactions between gases and moving bodies. This field primarily focuses on aerodynamic drag and lift, which are generated by the air flowing over and around objects. Engineers apply the principles of aerodynamics in various fields, such as the design of buildings and bridges. However, its most significant role lies in the development of aircraft and vehicles. The term aerodynamics is often also used to refer to gas dynamics. Gas dynamics concerns the motion of all gases, not just air. This field of study began to develop in the 18th century, although fundamental concepts such as drag had been recognized much earlier. Through mathematical analysis, wind tunnel experiments, and simulations, aerodynamics has established essential foundations that support the advancement of aviation and other technologies. [1]

1.2 Drag

When a rigid body moves in a gaseous or liquid medium, a certain force arises. This is called drag, and the objective is to overcome it. Drag occurs due to the relative motion between the body and the medium. From the perspective of drag, it does not matter whether the body moves through the medium or the medium flows around the body. In the case of a moving body, the resulting drag force partly comes from accelerating the fluid particles in front of it. In the other case, drag is generated by the collisions of the particles. During this process, kinetic energy is converted into pressure energy. [2]

1.3 3D Printing

3D printing has emerged as a new technology that has revolutionized the industry. It offers new solutions and pushes the boundaries of manufacturing possibilities. 3D printing designs can range from simple to complex, regardless of the material used, which may be metallic or non-metallic. In this process, filament material is added layer by layer. 3D printing software (slicer software) uses CAD models in .STL format as input data. During the slicing process, manufacturing parameters must be defined, including layer thickness, material quality, model orientation, and the infill pattern. At the end of the slicing process, a G-code file is generated. This file is then transferred to the 3D printer, and the printing process can begin. [3]

1.4 Materials

Various types of materials can be used. Plastics are the most widely used in both research and industry. They can be divided into two main categories: thermoplastics and thermosets. In 3D printing, two common processes are used: Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) and Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM). Most research focuses on FDM, as it is the most widely used method. This technology is applied both for functional parts and for prototyping. It plays an important role in the automotive industry, aerospace, and even healthcare. During the FDM process, thermoplastic materials are melted and then extruded layer by layer onto a heated build platform. In some cases, this technology may require post-processing, as gaps can form in the filament due to the nozzle diameter, which can reduce surface accuracy during printing. However, it is capable of producing complex geometries with minimal material waste. [4]

Thermoplastics can be divided into two groups based on their molecular structure: amorphous polymers and semicrystalline (partially crystalline) polymers. Thus, plastics can essentially be classified into three categories: amorphous polymers, semicrystalline polymers, and thermosetting plastics. Acrylonitrile

butadiene styrene (ABS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and polycarbonate (PC) are amorphous polymers. Polylactic acid (PLA) and PLA+ are semicrystalline polymers, while phenolic resins, silicone, and epoxy belong to thermosetting plastics. Most amorphous and semicrystalline polymers are widely used in FDM technology. Among the listed materials, ABS components are the most extensively studied. This material softens well when heated, has high strength and deformation capacity, is resistant to chemicals, and offers excellent dimensional stability. [4]

1.5 FEA (Finite Element Analysis)

Simulation processes are fundamentally based on CAD modeling, which relies on computer-aided design software for creating components. This is a very important step, as simulations must accurately reflect real-world conditions. In FEA (Finite Element Analysis) models, the material properties must be defined. All possible data and influencing factors should be provided in order to obtain valid predictions about material performance. In such cases, both mechanical loads and environmental effects are taken into account. Other critical factors also exist, such as boundary conditions and loading states. Their definition represents the virtual environment of the model and provides solutions for external forces, pressures, and temperatures. In finite element analysis, models can be divided into smaller, simpler elements, which helps to reduce the complexity of the governing equations. By calculating the resulting reactions, insight can be gained into the performance of the component. As a final step, the results must be evaluated and the obtained data analyzed. From this data, the structural integrity can be determined. Engineers assess the safety of components by examining stress distribution, deformation patterns, and other responses. Based on this, they can make informed decisions regarding improvements, material modifications, or other safety-related aspects. [5]

2. Research infrastructure CPS-LAB

The Vehicle Laboratory of the University of Debrecen, in cooperation with the Faculty of Engineering, was established to provide a dedicated location for research and development activities related to robotics and vehicle engineering. This research center enables the testing of custom systems in a controlled environment. The work of the Vehicle Laboratory is also supported by two major companies that play an important role in the automotive and technology sectors. One of them is the German BMW (Munich, Germany), and the other is KUKA Robotics (Augsburg, Germany). [6]

Figure 1. Vehicle Research Center [16]

Debrecen is undergoing transformations from both an industrial and economic perspective, driven primarily by the growth of automotive investments. In line with this development, the Vehicle Laboratory of the Faculty of Engineering at the University of Debrecen has set the goal of integrating electric vehicles into

its educational and research activities. This integration aligns with and adapts to modern industrial trends. [7]

The laboratory contains several robots used for research purposes. From an industrial perspective, some of the older models can be considered outdated. Most of the robots were designed according to the standards of their time; however, the controllers they are equipped with do not allow functions such as remote control. Due to their obsolescence, the hardware specifications and operating systems no longer support tasks such as image processing and data analysis. Among them is a Japanese-manufactured Sony SRX-611 robot, which is used for training and testing algorithms. [8]

The global pandemic and the microchip shortage had a significant impact on the professional work carried out in the laboratory. In order to ensure the continuity of research in the future, the laboratory had to be rebuilt on new foundations. The systems and robots needed to undergo digitalization and be integrated into the cyber-physical space. To meet the growing demands, the existing servers were no longer sufficient, which made the implementation of new data processing methods necessary. [9]

The Robot Laboratory of the research center also operates as an augmented reality (AR) isolated environment. It plays an important role in the building management and security network. The installed IP cameras can also be used as visual sensors with the help of a computer system. The central unit not only stores the recorded data but also has sufficient computational resources to perform CUDA-based image processing and decoding. A key feature of the system is that the controlled robot itself has no onboard detector. Its precise location is determined solely by the laboratory's camera system. Since cameras are installed on both floors of the building, the images can be processed from anywhere using the central computer. This setup enables the deployed AGV robot to operate autonomously in any part of the building when required. [10]

A laboratory cell has been set up for development and research tasks, primarily focusing on robotics and artificial intelligence. For this purpose, a KUKA KR5 serial kinematic robot has been installed. It has six degrees of freedom and a working envelope of approximately 8.4 m³. Due to its high precision, this robot has been used in industry for welding applications. Its maximum payload is only 5 kg, therefore it is suitable only for limited material handling tasks. The robot cell is equipped with three platforms that support material handling operations. The central element of the entire workstation is the conveyor belt, which ensures precise positioning of the objects. [11] The robot located here has already been the subject of several research projects within the department, covering areas such as control engineering and augmented reality (AR). KUKA robots are known for their reliability; however, they have a critical condition known as a "singularity point." If the robot passes through this point, it may trigger an emergency stop or behave unpredictably. This phenomenon is related to the mathematical foundations of the robot's software. [12]

The laboratory is not only focused on robotics, but also on finding solutions to other engineering problems, such as alternative energy generation. For example, a buoy system was developed that converts wave energy into usable electrical energy. The prototype includes a mechanical motion rectifier, a motion controller, an energy storage unit, and an electric generator. For the simulations, MATLAB models were created. As a result, a functioning energy conversion buoy was developed in the laboratory, demonstrating that this can be a viable alternative method for energy production. [13]

Biodegradable PLA composites reinforced with animal bone particles were also tested. The material was produced using a compression molding process. The amount of bone powder was varied, and the effects of pressure and temperature were also investigated. The results showed an improvement in mechanical properties. Materials with higher filler content exhibited increased strength; however, their flexibility significantly decreased. [14]

The Vehicle Laboratory has recently served as a site for research and development projects. Within this framework, an FDM-based 3D printer was designed and built for the production of custom components. FDM-type 3D printers are commonly used for prototyping and for low-volume production of parts. The printer located in the laboratory is of the TTT type, which defines the range of manufacturing processes that can be performed at a given time. [7] In the case of FDM printing systems, maintaining stable thermal resolution (or, in other words, temperature stability) is a very important factor. To ensure this, the 3D printer was equipped with a frame. [15]

3. Description of Processes

3.1 Function, placement and material selection of the spoiler

The subject of my project was an aftermarket spoiler designed for an Audi A4 B8 Avant vehicle [17]. My goal was to preserve the vehicle's original design while attempting to improve its fuel efficiency. In the case of station wagons, the airflow travels along the roof and then separates from the vehicle body at the rear. At this point, a turbulent wake is formed, which increases aerodynamic drag and consequently fuel consumption. The spoiler can be mounted onto the factory rear trunk spoiler of the vehicle. The function of my component is to maintain the airflow along the roof surface for a longer distance. By adding an additional lip to the vehicle, the resulting vortex is reduced in size, which leads to lower fuel consumption.

Table 1. Dimensions-own editing

Audi A4 B8 Avant dimensions	
Length	4703 mm
Width	1826 mm
Height	1436 mm
Frontal Area	2.2 m ²

The drag coefficient of the Audi A4 B8 Avant was $C_d=0.32$. The aerodynamic drag coefficient is determined using the following relationship:

$$C_d = \frac{2F_d}{\rho v^2 A}$$

Table 2.-Meaning of parameters-own editing

C_d	Drag coefficient
F_d	Aerodynamic drag force
ρ	Air density
v	Velocity
A	Frontal Area

By installing the spoiler, the drag coefficient is reduced by 1.73%, which in the long term results in a significant reduction in fuel consumption.

As mentioned earlier, the aftermarket spoiler can be mounted onto the factory rear spoiler, meaning it is located at the highest point of the vehicle. Since it is an external component, it is exposed to environmental influences such as solar radiation, dust, precipitation, and airflow. All of these factors affect the service life of the component. Mechanical loads can also be considered. First, bending can be highlighted. Due to the airflow, pressure forces the spoiler surface downward. At the mounting points and edges, higher bending moments may occur. Secondly, torsion should also be mentioned. Torsional loads can appear when the airflow is asymmetric or during cornering under crosswind conditions. In 3D printing, internal reinforcements can help counteract these effects.

The material selected for my design is ABS. It is widely used in the automotive industry for spoilers and

other components.

Density: $\approx 1.04 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Tensile strength: 30-45 MPa

Heat resistance: 90-105 °C

Based on these properties, it can be concluded that the material is capable of withstanding the required loads up to a certain speed range. Since it also has good heat resistance, it does not lose its shape on a hot car body, unlike PLA-based materials.

Figure 2. Spoiler installed-own editing

3.2 3D CAD Model design in Fusion [18]

The design was carried out using Autodesk Fusion 360. Before starting the design process, I downloaded a free model of the Audi A4 B8 Avant, which served as a reference base. This model made it possible to properly develop the spoiler geometry. As a first step, I started from a flat sketch with a width of 1 meter, corresponding to the size of the factory rear spoiler. By using mirrored symmetry, only one side of the component had to be designed, which significantly reduced the required design time. The final inclination angle of the spoiler was 5 degrees.

Most of the design work was carried out using the box display mode, as this view made it easier to shape the component during modeling. The smooth display mode was used when it was necessary to visualize the actual final appearance of the part. After obtaining the correct dimensions, the thickening of the model was performed. The selected wall thickness was 4 mm, which is considered an optimal value that ensures sufficient rigidity. If the part were thinner, additional reinforcements would be required. In the case of carbon fiber materials, thinner walls can be used due to their higher stiffness. For ABS-based materials, the recommended wall thickness typically ranges between 2–5 mm.

In the final steps, the curvature was refined to ensure a perfect fit on the vehicle. Using the Fillet command, the edges were rounded to improve both the geometry and the manufacturability of the part. Finally, the model was exported and saved in multiple file formats.

Figure 3. Spoiler design on the Audi-own editing

3.3 Creation of 3D CAD Model simulation in Fusion

The analysis of the designed component was also performed in Autodesk Fusion 360. The software includes a built-in Simulation workspace, where the structural behavior of the model can be evaluated. This allowed the entire workflow to remain seamless, without the need to use additional external software.

In Autodesk Fusion 360, switching from the Design workspace to Simulation mode can be done by clicking the “Design” tab. Here, the desired study type can be selected; in this case, the “Static Stress” analysis was chosen. In the next step, the material type must be defined. Initially, steel was assigned as the material, but since the spoiler is made of ABS, it was changed accordingly. This step is essential because the selected material determines how the component behaves under load during the simulation. After that, the boundary conditions had to be defined, including both the constraints (fixing conditions) and the applied loads.

Figure 4. Simulation steps-own editing

First, I defined the direction and magnitude of the applied load. In the initial test, I used a force of 7 N,

since the airflow does not significantly impact the spoiler but rather flows over its surface. A single load direction was assigned. Next, the constraints had to be defined, meaning the location of the fixed support. In my case, this was the underside of the spoiler, where it is attached to the vehicle. The following step was the creation of the mesh (meshing). The mesh is essential for running the simulation, as it discretizes the model into smaller elements, enabling numerical calculation of the structural response.

Figure 5. Mesh generation-own editing

Using the Pre-check function, it is possible to verify whether there are any issues with the model before running the simulation. If no problems are detected, the simulation can be executed.

Figure 6. Simulation with a single force-own editing

In the Safety Factor view, the spoiler appeared in blue, indicating that it would be safe to use. When switching to the Stress view, it is possible to observe where stresses occur within the component. The model remained in the green range, meaning that under low loads no significant changes occur, and the spoiler remains suitable for use.

In the second test, multiple load directions were applied—specifically three. Each of the forces was set to 100 N.

Figure 7. Simulation with multiple force-own editing

The first force acts horizontally on the front of the spoiler, the second acts horizontally on the top surface, and the third acts vertically on the top of the spoiler. In the Safety Factor view, the component also appeared in blue, indicating that it could theoretically withstand even higher loads. In the Stress view, the front region remained in the green range, while the upper part turned light blue. This indicates that the spoiler can withstand the applied loads and that the stress distribution is favorable.

3.4 Importing, setting up, and printing the designed 3D model in Ultimaker Cura (FDM based printing) [19]

After completing the analyses, I moved on to the 3D printing phase. For printing, I used Ultimaker Cura, as it is suitable for beginners. The spoiler model was imported in .STL format. Since the component was too large to print at full scale, I decided to create a 1:10 scale prototype. This reduced size easily fits within the build volume of a standard 3D printer.

Figure 8. Printing settings-own editing

A layer height of 0.12 mm was selected to achieve the smoothest possible aerodynamic curves of the spoiler, minimizing the need for post-processing such as sanding. An infill density of 20% was used, with a Gyroid pattern, as it provides uniform stiffness in all directions. The wall thickness was set to 1.6 mm, which further

increases the rigidity of the part. Support structures were configured as Tree supports, which ensure minimal contact with the model and are easier to remove after printing. Build plate adhesion was also enabled to keep the object securely in place during the printing process. After configuring all the parameters in Ultimaker Cura, the estimated printing time was 1 hour and 14 minutes.

Figure 9. Spoiler print preview-own editing

Figure 10. Printing time and material usage-own editing

4. Conclusion

During my work, I presented an Audi A4 B8 Avant and defined its exact dimensions. These measurements had to be taken into account during the design of the spoiler. The component I designed can be mounted on the top of the trunk lid, more specifically on the factory rear spoiler. This results in an extended roofline, improving the overall aerodynamic shape of the vehicle.

As mentioned before, turbulent vortices form at the rear of station wagons, which increase aerodynamic drag and consequently fuel consumption. The purpose of the designed component is to further guide the airflow and delay flow separation from the surface. Due to the designed model, the turbulent wake is shifted further rearward, resulting in smaller vortex structures. As a result, fuel consumption decreases by a few percent. This effect becomes particularly important during highway driving, where higher aerodynamic forces act on the vehicle.

The design was carried out using Autodesk Fusion 360, for which an additional reference model of an Audi A4 B8 Avant was downloaded free of charge. This served as a basis for the proportional design of the spoiler. Mirrored symmetry was used during modeling, allowing work to be carried out only on one side of the component, which significantly reduced design time. The box display and smooth display modes were alternated in order to continuously evaluate the actual appearance of the geometry during development. The final inclination angle of the spoiler was set to 5 degrees, which is sufficient to redirect the airflow more effectively. As a final refinement step, the curvature was further adjusted. The resulting model fitted well to the original lines of the vehicle.

The next step was the simulation phase, which was also carried out in Autodesk Fusion 360. The software provides a built-in Simulation environment, where the behaviour of the model under different forces can be tested. Since both design and simulation were performed within the same program, a significant amount

of time was saved, as no additional simulation software had to be learned or used. The selected material was defined as ABS. The directions and magnitudes of the applied forces were set, along with the fixed support locations representing the mounting points. In the final step, the mesh was generated, after which the simulation was executed. In both analyzed cases, the CAD model successfully withstood the applied loads, meaning that the tests were successful. The design and the chosen material met the mechanical requirements. Even under extreme wind conditions, the structure is capable of ensuring safe operation.

Next, I imported my CAD model into Ultimaker Cura. This is a 3D printing slicer program that is easy to use and also recommended for beginners. The file had to be imported in .STL format, as this is the required format for printing. The spoiler was scaled down to a 1:10 ratio, since it would not have fit within the printer's build volume otherwise. As this is a prototype, the reduced scale was considered acceptable. A layer height of 0.12 mm was selected to ensure the smoothest possible aerodynamic surfaces of the spoiler, minimizing the need for post-processing such as sanding. An infill density of 20% was used, with a Gyroid pattern, which provides uniform stiffness in all directions. Tree supports were selected, as they provide minimal contact with the model, use less material, and are easier to remove after printing. Adhesion was also enabled to ensure that the model remains fixed on the build plate during printing. The estimated printing time was 1 hour and 14 minutes, with a material usage of approximately 1.29 meters of filament. The reduced scale proved to be an efficient solution, as it allowed the geometry of the spoiler to be evaluated in real space without compromising structural integrity through multi-part assembly.

In summary, the designed component fits properly onto the target vehicle. It is capable of withstanding the applied loads, and the ABS material proved to be a suitable choice. The printing process showed that with the correct settings, a reliable prototype can be produced while using a relatively small amount of material. The project demonstrated that the systems and manufacturing equipment available in the Vehicle Laboratory are suitable for the development of automotive components.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

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**Vehicle Research Center:
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